

“Word of Mouth as a Marketing Strategy”

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Abstract

The research is to study and understand the customer’s influence on word of mouth in marketing of a product or a service and how word of mouth helps in analyzing and creating more impact on the organization.

Word of mouth being one of the simplest forms of marketing and is one of the cost effective methods of marketing a product in an organization impacts the customers and it helps the organization to create impact on its brand in the market.

Although there is both positive and negative impact on the brand through word of mouth it mainly helps the customers to recognize the brand and thus gives more effect on the other customers.

Keywords: Cost effective, Influence, Brand

Objectives

- Is there a greater effect through word of mouth in marketing a products
- How customers are aware word of mouth marketing
- How to build a brand image through word of mouth

Introduction

From the beginning humans have always engaged in communicating with people, it includes sharing of your knowledge, experiences, talking about anything and everything. In this process it becomes very easy to share your views, beliefs, or any kind of advices which helps in the building up of informal communications. This makes the process of communication very easier, talking about their last experiences, or any kind of experiences about a product usage, the websites available and the kind of services that are offered by various entities.

There has been a lot progress over the years in the usage of internet and its various applications, which has made the process of communication more easier for people to share and transfer knowledge from any part of the world.

In this process people gather information and opinions about a product which is known as word-of-mouth communication, it

includes all the positive and negative statements made by a customer on the basis of his experiences. Consumers are always keen on responding, creating and exchanging of information among people which makes word-of-mouth communication more effectively practiced. Word of mouth technique has not only enhanced the process of communication locally but also globally where people engage in sharing and exchanging information and experiences through effective networking tools which makes the process of knowledge sharing more easy and reliable.

Methodology

This examination utilizes a quantitative approach that utilizes a shut - finished system of research outline. The fundamental point of the exploration is to direct an overview on the overall population, keeping in mind the end goal to comprehend “Word of mouth impact as a marketing strategy” in their observation. To comprehend the perspectives of individuals the review is led on the web and the poll comprises of 10 questions which are shut finished and the same is examined, broke down, established and closed. Review is directed with a Sample size of “80 respondents” by utilizing Scaling strategy of estimation. The examples are attracted such a route, to the point that there are 70 individuals from young people/understudies gathering and 10 individuals from working gathering. The example configuration utilized in this review is Convenience Sample Design, as the examples are drawn according to our benefit.

Analysis of Data

Poll – Online review with 10 inquiries with test measure as 80 respondents.

Investigation and Calculations, Analyzed utilizing Measurement of Scaling Technique based

- Youth/Students –70 i.e (87.5%)
- Based on working gathering – 10 i.e (12.5%)

Responses of the Questionnaire by the Respondents

Do you feel online marketing has more impact than word of mouth?

80 responses

What is your opinion about word of mouth marketing as a strategy

78 responses

it is very effective

It inculcate trust among the customer

It's good that people recommend products And it's easy to buy such products rather than looking for new products

Sometimes word of mouth isn't enough and edge over the brand should be done through online

Word of mouth is one of the easy ways to market and it's good

It is very imp as many of the people interact with their friends and family before buying any product from certain brands in this way there can be traffic for the particular brand.

Word of mouth is better when compared to online marketing

Online is better

it is an effective strategy for marketing

Findings

- 93% of the respondents felt that the word of mouth has a more impact compared to other forms of marketing.
- 68% of the respondents said that the urge to buy products may arise due through word of mouth.
- 55% of the respondents feel that most of the brands they are aware of is through word of mouth rather than any other kind of brand marketing
- 20% of the respondents say that there is more trust on the products through the word of mouth which further creates a chain of customers.
- 12% of the respondents say that it makes the customers aware and it is of the most cost effective tool as a strategy

Suggestions

Through the review directed on “Word of mouth impact as a marketing strategy”. In view of the reactions given by the respondents, the different recommendations can be given

- a) Though most of the respondents feel that word of mouth is the best tool or strategy the improvement through online also plays a crucial role in current scenario
- b) The customers will be more aware of the products when the brand creates a huge impact through word of mouth and chain reaction of it
- c) Word of mouth marketing is as important as any other marketing and keeping that in view the simplicity of the products will spread through word of mouth quicker and makes it more reliable than online marketing.

Limitation of the Study Conducted

- a) Since the questionnaire is taken on a smaller number, we can't have any significant attitude on a larger scale. The outcomes may vary accordingly
- b) Time is one of the constraints.
- c) The attitudes, styles and preferences of the customers keep changing according to the environment which would change in the future period.